

Synthesis of tributyl Sn^{IV}-Al^{III}- μ -oxoisopropoxide and its derivatives with salicylates

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Abstract : The compound tributyl Sn^{IV}-Al^{III}- μ -oxoisopropoxide [Bu₃SnOAl(OPrⁱ)₂] was prepared by refluxing equimolar amounts of tributyltin acetate and aluminum isopropoxide in toluene. The reactions of [Bu₃SnOAl(OPrⁱ)₂] with methyl/ethyl/phenyl salicylates in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 ratios resulted in derivatives of the type [Bu₃SnOAl(OPrⁱ)(RSal)] and [Bu₃SnOAl(RSal)₂] (where RSal is deprotonated methyl/ethyl/phenyl salicylate) respectively. The μ -oxo compound and its salicylate derivatives were characterized by elemental analysis, molecular weight measurements and spectral studies (¹H NMR, ²⁷Al NMR and IR). The studies reveal that the compound [Bu₃SnOAl(OPrⁱ)₂] and its salicylate derivatives are dimeric.

Keywords : Oxoisopropoxide, tin(IV), aluminium(III).

It is well established that metal and mixed metal alkoxides are amongst the best precursors for the synthesis of metal and mixed metal oxide nanoparticles respectively by sol-gel method^{1,2}. Due to their high surface area, these oxides have been found to be exceptional adsorbent and catalysts³⁻⁶. The class of compound namely, bimetallic- μ -oxoalkoxides of the type [(RO)₂Al-O-M-O-Al(OR)₂] (M = Mg, Ca, Mn, Fe, Ni, Co, Zn, and Mo; R = isopropyl or t-butyl) have been systematically synthesized⁷⁻⁹. These μ -oxoalkoxide display amazingly high solubility in common organic solvents and undergo facile hydrolysis. These properties make them excellent single source precursors for the synthesis of mixed metal oxides by sol-gel method. Recently, synthesis of homogeneously dispersed bimetallic oxides in nano crystalline or amorphous form has been reported by Klabunde *et al.*¹⁰. Apart from their role as precursors for mixed metal oxides the bimetallic- μ -oxoalkoxides of transition metals have been found to rank among the best catalysts for the polymerization of heterocyclic monomers like lactones, oxiranes, thiranes and epoxides¹¹⁻¹³. Owing to the ever-growing importance of hetero metallic alkoxides and oxoalkoxides it was considered worthwhile to synthesize [Bu₃SnOAl(OPrⁱ)₂] and to further gain an insight into its structure, its reactions have been carried out with different salicylates.

Results and discussion

[Bu₃SnOAl(OPrⁱ)₂] has been synthesized by refluxing tributyltin acetate and aluminum isopropoxide in 1 : 1

molar ratio and its salicylate derivatives have been synthesized by refluxing [Bu₃SnOAl(OPrⁱ)₂] with different salicylates in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio. The molecular weight measurement of the compound [Bu₃SnOAl(OPrⁱ)₂] and its salicylate derivatives suggest that they are dimeric in nature and are probably linked by oxygen bridges.

IR spectra :

The sharp bands at 1590 and 1440 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{C}=\text{O})$, respectively in tributyltin acetate have been found to be absent in the [Bu₃SnOAl(OPrⁱ)₂] compound indicating the removal of acetyl group. The compound [Bu₃SnOAl(OPrⁱ)₂] and its 1 : 1 salicylate derivatives show absorption bands in the region 1360-1340 cm⁻¹ and 1150-1165 cm⁻¹ are characteristic of *gem*-dimethyl portion and combination band $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O}+\text{OPr}^i)$ of the isopropoxy group respectively^{14,15}. However, these bands are absent in 1 : 2 salicylate derivatives indicating complete replacement of both the isopropoxy groups. A broad band in the region ~3100 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ in salicylates was found absent in derivatives of [Bu₃SnOAl(OPrⁱ)₂] indicates the deprotonation of these ligands. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ band appearing in salicylates at ~1650 cm⁻¹ shows a downward shift of 15-25 cm⁻¹ in the derivatives, indicating the coordination of the carbonyl oxygen of the salicylate to the metal atom. A strong band observed at 1245 cm⁻¹ in salicylates due to phenolic $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ vibrations is shifted 15-20 cm⁻¹ higher in the derivatives indicating bond formation of phenolic oxygen of salicylate to the metal atom. A number of bands ob-

served in the μ -oxo compound and its salicylate derivatives in the region $700\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to M–O stretching vibrations¹⁶. The bands related to phenyl groups in the derivatives are observed at their usual positions in the IR spectra. The IR spectra of the derivatives indicate that salicylates behave as monobasic bidentate ligands.

¹H NMR spectra :

A peak observed at δ 2.3 ppm in tributyltin acetate due to methyl protons of the acetate group is absent in the μ -oxo compound $[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ confirms the replacement of the acetyl group. The ¹H NMR spectrum of the compound $[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ and its 1 : 1 derivative show number of peaks in the region δ 0.7–1.2 ppm are due to inter mixing of methyl protons of the isopropoxy groups and protons of the butyl groups bonded to tin atom. A multiplet centered at δ 4.1 ppm in $[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ is due to methine proton of the isopropoxy groups. This peak is found to overlap with the peak observed at $\sim\delta$ 3.8 ppm due to methyl and methylene protons of methyl and ethyl salicylate in 1 : 1 derivative respectively. A fairly sharp singlet is observed at $\sim\delta$ 3.8 ppm and a quartet centered at $\sim\delta$ 3.6 ppm are assigned to methyl and methylene protons in 1 : 2 derivative of $[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ with methyl and ethyl salicylates respectively. This confirms the substitution of both the isopropoxy groups of tributyl tin^{IV}-Al^{III}- μ -oxoisopropoxide. A broad singlet at $\sim\delta$ 12.8 ppm due to phenolic proton in the salicylate is found absent in all derivatives confirms their deprotonation. The signals due to phenyl ring protons of salicylate moiety are observed at their usual positions (δ 6.4–7.6 ppm) in all the derivatives.

²⁷Al NMR spectra :

The ²⁷Al NMR spectrum of $[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ shows a singlet at δ 62 ppm indicating tetrahedral environment about the Al atom and is surrounded by four oxygen atoms¹⁷. Whereas, the ²⁷Al NMR spectra of salicylate derivatives of $[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ shows a singlet at $\sim\delta$ 1 ppm indicates an octahedral environment about the aluminum atom and is coordinated by six oxygen atoms¹⁸. This is probably due to the replacement of both isopropoxy groups on the same aluminium atom. Since the 5-coordinated Al produced by replacement of first isopropoxy group in the dimeric structure is relatively unstable as compared to tetrahedral and octahedral coordination. Thus the second isopropoxy group of the compound tributyl tin^{IV}-Al^{III}- μ -oxoisopropoxide is then displaced from the same Al atom. The ²⁷Al NMR also suggest that the dominant species in the solution is the one in which aluminium

Fig. 1

Fig. 2a

Fig. 2b

Deprotonated Salicylate =

is octahedrally coordinated with six oxygen atoms¹⁸.

On the basis of above spectral studies following tentative structures have been proposed for μ -oxo compound $[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ (Fig. 1) and its derivatives $[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)(\text{RSal})]$ (Fig. 2a) and $[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{RSal})_2]$ (Fig. 2b).

Experimental

Stringent precautions were taken to exclude moisture throughout the present work. The general technique and physical measurements were carried out as described elsewhere¹⁹. The aluminum isopropoxide was prepared by reported method²⁰. The solvents, salicylates and tributyltin acetate (Aldrich) were made dry and purified prior to their use. The isopropyl acetate and isopropanol were estimated oxidimetrically²¹ while aluminium and tin were estimated gravimetrically. The molecular weights were determined in dry benzene using cryoscopic method (depression in freezing point). The infrared spectra were recorded as direct film on a Perkin-Elmer 1710 FTIR spectrometer, over a range $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The ¹H NMR

Table 1. Reactions of $[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ with salicylates

Sl. no.	Compd. g (mmol)	Ligand g (mmol)	Molar ratio	Refluxing time	Product	Analysis : Found (Calcd.)		
						Pr ⁱ OH (g)	Al (%)	Sn (%)
1.	$[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ 0.623 (1.38)	HMeSal 0.210 (1.38)	1 : 1	3	$[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)(\text{MeSal})]$	0.079 (0.083)	5.01 (4.97)	21.21 (21.92)
2.	$[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ 0.588 (1.30)	HMeSal 0.396 (2.61)	1 : 2	5½	$[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{MeSal})_2]$	0.153 (0.156)	4.20 (4.25)	17.94 (18.74)
3.	$[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ 0.612 (1.36)	HEtSal 0.225 (1.36)	1 : 1	3½	$[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)(\text{EtSal})]$	0.080 (0.081)	4.67 (4.85)	21.24 (21.36)
4.	$[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ 0.427 (0.95)	HEtSal 0.314 (1.89)	1 : 2	6	$[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{EtSal})_2]$	0.109 (0.114)	3.86 (4.07)	16.89 (17.95)
5.	$[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ 0.590 (1.31)	HPhSal 0.260 (1.31)	1 : 1	3½	$[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)(\text{PhSal})]$	0.080 (0.078)	4.24 (4.46)	18.95 (19.67)
6.	$[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ 0.379 (0.84)	HPhSal 0.360 (1.68)	1 : 2	6½	$[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{PhSal})_2]$	0.105 (0.101)	3.45 (3.56)	15.34 (15.68)

HMeSal = Methyl salicylate; HEtSal = Ethyl salicylate; HPhSal = Phenyl salicylate.

spectra were recorded on Varian Gemini 300 MHz, while ²⁷Al NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker 400 MHz.

Reaction of Bu_3SnOAc with $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ in 1 : 1 molar ratio :

Bu_3SnOAc (3.682 g, 10.55 mmol) and $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ (2.157 g, 10.56 mmol) were refluxed in 1 : 1 molar ratio in toluene (~80 ml) for 6 h on an oil bath (temperature ~130°C). The reaction can be represented by the following equation.

The isopropyl acetate formed during the course of reaction was continuously removed from ~78 °C to the boiling point of toluene (110 °C). This was collected and estimated oxidimetrically²¹ to check the completion of the reaction. The excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure (60 °C/1 mm). The product was redissolved in benzene and slow evaporation of benzene resulted in a pale yellow glassy solid (yield 98%). The μ -oxo compound was found to be soluble in common organic solvents such as CHCl_3 and C_6H_6 , highly susceptible to hydrolysis and decomposed on heating (~170 °C) Analysis (Found : OPrⁱ, 25.98; Sn, 25.72; Al, 5.86. Calcd : OPrⁱ, 26.16; Sn, 26.37; Al, 5.99%).

Reaction of $[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ with methyl salicylate (HMeSal) in 1 : 1 molar ratio :

$[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ (0.623 g, 1.38 mmol) and methyl

salicylate (0.210 g, 1.38 mmol) were refluxed in benzene (~60 ml) for 3 h on an oil bath (temperature ~100 °C). The reaction can be represented by the following equation.

(n = 1 or 2; HMeSal = methyl salicylate)

The liberated isopropanol was continuously fractionated at 72–78 °C as binary azeotrope of isopropanol-benzene. The azeotrope formed during the course of reaction was collected and checked for completion of the reaction. The excess of solvent was removed at 40 °C/1 mm pressure. A pale yellow solid product was obtained. The preparation of other salicylate derivatives of $[\text{Bu}_3\text{SnOAl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]$ in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios were carried out by a similar procedure and their analytical data along with metal and liberated isopropanol estimations have been summarized in the Table 1. All the derivatives were found to be soluble in common organic solvents, moisture sensitive and decomposed on heating.

References

- G. H. P. Liliane, *Polyhedron*, 1994, 13, 1185.
- L. L. Hench and J. K. West, *Chem. Rev.*, 1990, 90, 33.
- J. V. Stark, D. G. Park, I. Lagadic and K. J. Klabunde, *J. Chem. Mater.*, 1996, 9, 1904.
- K. J. Klabunde, J. V. Stark, O. Koper, C. Mohs, D. G. Park, S. Decker, Y. Jiang, I. Lagadic and D. Zhang, *J. Phys. Chem.*

- 1996, **100**, 12142.
5. O. Koper, I. Lagadic and K. J. Klabunde. *Chem. Mater.*, 1997, **9**, 838.
 6. O. Koper and K. J. Klabunde. US Pat. 6057488, 1999.
 7. T. Ouhadi, J. P. Bioul, Ch. Stevens, R. Warin, L. Hocks and Ph. Teyssie. *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **19**, 203.
 8. Harish K Sharma and Pramesh N. Kapoor. *Polyhedron*, 1988, **4**, 1389.
 9. R. C. Mehrotra and A. Singh. *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1996, **1**.
 10. Pramesh N. Kapoor, David Heroux, Ravichandra S. Mulukulta, Valdimir Zaikovskii and Kenneth J. Klabunde. *J. Mater. Chem.*, 2003, **13**, 1.
 11. J. Heuschen, R. Jerome and Ph. Teyssie, *Macromolecules*, 1981, **14**, 242.
 12. A. Hamitou, R. Jerome, A. J. Hubert and Ph. Teyssie, *Macromolecules*, 1973, **6**, 651.
 13. T. Ouhadi, A. Hamitou, R. Jerome and Ph. Teyssie, *J. Polymer. Sci., Polymer. Chem. Ed.*, 1977, **15**, 865.
 14. C. T. Lynch, K. S. Masdiyanni, J. S. Smith and W. J. Grawford, *Anal. Chem.*, 1964, **36**, 2332.
 15. V. A. Koznov, N. I. Kuzlova, N. Ya. Turova and Yu. S. Nekrasov, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1979, **24**, 1526.
 16. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1986.
 17. D. Mueller. Hoebbel and W. Gessner. *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1981, **84**, 2.
 18. V. J. Shiner (Jr.), D. Whittaker and V. F. Fernandes. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 23.
 19. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman, London, 1989.
 20. W. G. Young, W. H. Hartung and F. S. Crossley, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **56**, 100.
 21. D. C. Bradley, F. M. A. Halim and Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3450.